

LEARNING VOCABULARY WITH “BUNCEE ADD SMART” AMONG STUDENTS IN REMEDIATION PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

Buncee is a creation and presentation tool for students and educators to create interactive classroom content, allowing learners of all ages to visualize concepts and communicate creatively. The purpose of this experimental study is to examine the effect of using “Buncee Add Smart” in teaching language subjects. In language, on many occasions, the known vocab is used to add understanding to the new vocab among the students in a remediation program for language learning. These students experienced difficulties in learning new vocabulary and had low performances in academic subjects particularly language subjects. A total of 10 students will be participating in a pre-test and post-test with none-equivalent groups quasi-experimental study for learning vocabulary in Malay language. With a variety of graphics and media tools, students in the experimental group were able to develop their imaginations for improving their creativity while having fun. The “Buncee Add Smart” was described as an interactive, drag and drop interface which helps educators create amazing multimedia projects and presentations to increase interactivity and flip the classroom. With this amazing digital tool, it also can add all kinds of elements including animations, stickers, text, drawings, voice and even videos to share around their learning. Drawing from the results of this study, teachers could use “Buncee Add Smart” for creating new innovation with digital tools. The findings indicated that “Buncee Add Smart” could help pupils to learn vocabulary more easily and effectively while enjoying the Educators are able to differentiate the instruction of class’s learning through diverse students’ learning styles such as auditory, kinesthetic and visual.

Keywords: low performances, educational, learning styles, auditory, kinesthetic, visual

1. Introduction

A remedial program is an instructional program designed for students who have fallen behind? lagging behind their peers? in school performance and they have average intellectual abilities. Typically, under remedial program in Malaysia comprised of those who are struggling with one subject area like reading, writing or mathematics. Remedial programs are essential to be designed to provide students some individual attentions. They need to build their skills and their

confidence so that they can live up to their potential. It also offers students special one-on-one attention that is much more in demand. Almost all the students today find it difficult to sit down and stay focused in class because the delivery of traditional lectures does not grasp the attention of all learning types. In Malaysia's public schools today, there will be mainstream remedial programs into the class offerings and teachers typically need to learn special remediation skills and methods and smaller class sizes.

Remedial education works on the basis of addressing each learner's difficulties in small groups. As a qualified remedial teacher told us for this article: "Remedial education is definitely not more worksheets. It is the use of practical, hands-on where possible, auditory and visual stimuli." It would ensure that learners under your care are getting the attention they need and becoming better than doing nothing. According to Charles W. Elio, 'Books are the quietest and most constant of friends; they are the most accessible and wisest of counselors, and the most patient of teachers'.

From time to time people have wondered why reading is important. It is important to realize that struggling with vital reading skills is not a sign of low intelligence. For example, John Corcoran, who wrote *The Teacher Who Couldn't Read*, [1] is a very intelligent man. He graduated from High School and College, later he became a popular High School teacher and a successful businessman, all without being able to read. Remedial pupils actually are highly intelligent people who have struggled with reading. However, when they are properly taught with special educational tools, most of them can learn to read easily and quickly.

Learning new vocabulary is about listening and understanding as well as working out what is shown in attractive and colourful graphics. Through hearing, children are exposed to a wide range of words. This helps them build their own vocabulary and improve their understanding when they listen, which is essential as they start to read. It is important for them to understand the meaning of the vocabulary too. Even if pupils do not understand every word, they will hear new sounds, words and phrases which they can then try out, copying what they have heard. Irrespective of whether pupils are only just beginning to learn to read or whether they are fluent, teachers always play an important role in helping to keep them interested in learning new vocabulary. With full efforts, find out what special tools could interest and help them to learn well that will be engaging and fun and spend time with them together.

Vocabulary refers to the collection of words that a person knows and uses. Vocabulary development is the process of acquiring new words. Children start to know the vocabulary from preschool and first grade is often a strong indicator of their reading comprehension in later grades. That's why it's so important to focus on building vocabulary skills throughout reading instruction. There are many ways to improve and increase vocabulary skills. With "Bunce Add smart", building vocabulary skills is fun and interesting! It uses exciting, multimedia activities to teach standards-based reading & vocabulary lessons as part of a language arts curriculum.

2. Literature Reviews

2.1 Connectivism

Connectivism releases the learner from the cognitive practices of acquiring knowledge through experience, study, and receiving instruction. (Abik et al., 2012). [2] Connectivism allows students to incorporate electronic devices for the "off-site" storage of information, treating the role of

memory differently than prior learning theories. With connectivism, technology is permitted to become part of the student's internal learning process. While older learning theories have their place in the communication of basic knowledge, instruction must embrace connectivism to ensure that knowledge in the 21st century will be properly conveyed (Abik et al., 2012). [2]

Before technology appeared on the pedagogical landscape, the cognitivist method was delivery of instruction by a teacher-centered method. Students were receivers of the information. In the constructivist model, learners became dynamic members in the development of their learning while the teacher served as facilitator (Stavredes, 2011). [3] In the post-technology world, Siemens proposed "connectivism as a learning theory for the digital age" (Siemens, 2004, p.1). [4] In connectivism, knowledge is distributed across networks where connections and connectedness inform learning. Heavily grounded in technology, connectivism is a learning theory based on the acquisition of the knowledge focused on the future, not the past (Siemens, 2012). [5] [6]

Learning theory and internet technologies are some of the components of what is considered an online educational -experience. Although the teacher, student, and content generally remain the same, the transmutation of student-teacher-content pedagogical triangle of the cognitive theory to the student-teacher-network-content tetrahedron of the connectivist learning theory invites the network into the educational process (Fiore, 2017). [7] Whether a student is learning in an online program or distance education course, teaching and learning can be improved by the incorporation of connectivist learning theory.

Connectivists such as Siemens and Downes tend to be somewhat vague about the role of teachers or instructors, as the focus of connectivism is more on individual participants, networks and the flow of information and the new forms of knowledge that result. The main purpose of a teacher appears to be to provide the initial learning environment and context that brings learners together, and to help learners construct their own personal learning environments to enable them to connect to 'successful' networks, with the assumption that learning will automatically occur as a result, through exposure to the flow of information and the individual's autonomous reflection on its meaning. There is no need for formal institutions to support this kind of learning, especially since such learning often depends heavily on social media readily available to all participants.

Different theories of learning reflect different positions on the nature of knowledge. With the possible exception of connectivism, there is some form of empirical evidence to support each of the theories of learning outlined here. However, while the theories suggest different ways in which all people learn, they do not automatically tell teachers or instructors how to teach. Indeed, theories of behaviourism, cognitivism and constructivism were all developed outside of education, in experimental labs, psychology, neuroscience, and psychotherapy respectively. Educators have had to work out how to move from the theoretical position to the practical one of applying these theories within an educational experience. In other words, they have had to develop teaching methods that build on such learning theories. The next section of the book examines a range of teaching methods that have been developed, their epistemological roots, and their implications for teaching in a digital age.

2.2 VARK Learning Styles

Every student is totally different. It is readily observable that different students have different learning styles, that some students retain information easily when it is presented to them via a

format or method that may confound one of their classmates. To help educators develop strategies for reaching every student in their classroom effectively, educational scholars have devised various typologies of different styles of learning. Below, read about VARK, a commonly cited schema for assessing students' learning preferences, and the four different learning styles that comprise it, and discover some strategies for engaging with each type of learner.

The acronym "VARK" is used to describe four modalities of student learning that were described in a 1992 study by Neil D. Fleming and Coleen E. Mills. [8] These different learning styles—visual, auditory, reading/writing and kinesthetic—were identified after thousands of hours of classroom observation. The authors also created an accompanying questionnaire for educators to give to students to help them identify and understand their own learning preferences.

2.2.1 Visual Learners

Students who best internalize and synthesize information when it is presented to them in a graphic depiction of meaningful symbols are described as visual learners. They may respond to arrows, charts, diagrams and other visualizations of information hierarchy, but not necessarily to photographs or videos. [9] Because visual learners tend to be holistic learners who process information best when it is presented to them as a robust whole rather than piecemeal, they tend to see positive educational outcomes when they are presented with summarizing charts and diagrams rather than sequential slides of information. [10]

2.2.2 Auditory Learners

Auditory (or aural) learners are most successful when they are given the opportunity to hear information presented to them vocally. Because students with this learning style may sometimes opt not to take notes during class in order to maintain their unbroken auditory attention, educators can erroneously conclude that they are less engaged than their classmates. However, these students may simply have decided that note-taking is a distraction and that their unbroken attention is a more valuable way for them to learn. [11] Auditory learning is a two-way street: Students who fall into this modality often find success in group activities where they are asked to discuss course materials vocally with their classmates, and they may benefit from reading their written work aloud to themselves to help them think it through. [9]

2.2.3 Reading/Writing Learners

Students who work best in the reading/writing modality demonstrate a strong learning preference for the written word. This includes both written information presented in class in the form of handouts and PowerPoint slide presentations as well as the opportunity to synthesize course content in the completion of written assignments. [12] This modality also lends itself to conducting research online, as many information-rich sources on the internet are relatively text-heavy. [9] Reading/writing-oriented students should be encouraged to take copious notes during classroom lectures to help them both process information and have an easier time recalling it later.

2.2.4 Kinesthetic Learners

Kinesthetic learners are hands-on, participatory learners who need to take a physically active role in the learning process in order to achieve their best educational outcomes. They are sometimes referred to as "tactile learners," but this can be a bit of a misnomer; rather than simply utilizing

touch, kinesthetic learners tend to engage all of their senses equally in the process of learning. [13] Because of their active nature, kinesthetic learners often have the most difficult time succeeding in conventional classroom settings. Some educators have found success encouraging kinesthetic learners to utilize flashcards for subjects like math and English to make rote memorization into an interactive experience. These students also often thrive in scientific subjects with lab components, as the skills-based, instructional training that occurs in these settings engages them in productive ways. [13]

2.2.5 Several Different Learning Styles

Few things in life fall into easily delineated schema, and learning preferences are no exception. In fact, studies estimate that somewhere between 50 and 70 percent of the population have affinities to several different styles of learning. [14] These people are called “multimodal learners” and tend to succeed in classroom settings that engage them with multiple learning styles alternately or in concert with one another. Just because students can succeed with different learning styles does not necessarily mean that they should be engaged with more than one on most occasions. However, while today’s media-rich environment has made multimodal learning easier than ever before, recent studies recommend some caution and care when introducing multimedia instructional design into the classroom. Generally speaking, multimedia should be treated thoughtfully as a means to a specific educational goal rather than an end itself, and multimodal, interactive instruction should be reserved for more complex topics than for basic memorization and skill-building. [15]

2.4 Improving Visual Reading Strategies

2.4.1 Buncee for Education

Buncee for Education is a versatile platform where teachers and students create and share multimedia presentation boards by adding Buncees or slides. The site (iOS and Chrome app, too) offers simple, free-to-try tools for creating slideshows that can be embedded or shared via email, social media, QR code, or URL. The simple interface helps students create slideshows easily. Students start by naming the project and then work through the menus to add content to the slides in the form of drawings, animations, videos, emojis, stickers, and tons of other design features. There's an extensive image library as well as options to search for online images, music, and videos, though some content may be inappropriate or blocked by school or district filters. Just be sure to teach kids about giving proper credit for content they find online. Users can also get inspiration from the blog and make copies of boards contained in the gallery.

With so many choices, it's easy to come up with ideas for engaging presentations, but using effective design techniques will be paramount to the tool's effectiveness. An abundance of visual options could lead to poorly designed or cluttered presentations. When assigning projects to students, teachers should be clear about their expectations. Provide examples, modeling and scaffolding to help support students' creation. Encourage students to explore the gallery or use available templates as they develop their design skills. Within the tool, give students limits so that the visual resources enhance, rather than overpower, their projects.

Buncee is an incredible technology tool which is used in the classroom. Educators have utilized Buncee in all subjects such as Mathematics for students to explain a concept they are learning. They have also utilized creating a video to explain the concept they have been working

on during class. Students have thoroughly enjoyed using Buncee in this way. As a teacher, this makes it clear which students thoroughly understand the concept and which students would benefit from another lesson. Teachers may create vocabulary slides with vocabulary words. Their slides can have the word and definition. Additionally, it was able to select a background, sticker, and animation that supported the vocabulary word and definition. They become completely engrossed in the process. Students have worked collaboratively after reading a text. Students also have chances to create projects using Buncee. These projects have focused on the animal collections, spelling book, and port of entry projects just to name a few. The possibilities are truly endless with Buncee.

Create Buncees for online storytime by recording yourself reading a book and including supplemental clips and activities to enhance comprehension. Foreign language teachers can take advantage of the practically limitless content options to design or assign presentations where students video themselves speaking, practicing vocabulary, or reading aloud. In any subject area, give kids a chance to teach each other by using the comment feature to provide feedback, improve writing, or correct inaccuracies. There are some examples of “Buncee Add smart” as below for improving students' learning.

PERKATAAN KVK (MALAY VERSION)

<https://app.edu.buncee.com/buncee/ff397c4151c04f5d98eb830e42732185>

Figure 1 : The example of “Buncee add smart” in teaching the new vocabulary

Figure 2 : The example of “Buncee add smart” in teaching the new sentence

2.4.2 Visual-spatial Skills

Visual-spatial skills help individuals find their orientation in space through taking in information from the world around them and organizing that visual information to create an understanding of meaningful patterns. Visual-spatial skills allow us to perceive the visual information in the

environment, to represent it internally, and integrate it with past experiences, to derive meaning and understanding, and to perform manipulations and transformations on those perceptions. Deficits in visual-spatial skills can have a pervasive impact on a student's abilities. These skills are important in helping us think abstractly, visualize verbal information, and recognize how details are related to big picture ideas. Weaknesses in this area can impact basic skills such as letter formation, note taking, and simple math computation as well as more complex skill areas such as reading comprehension, math (e.g., estimation, geometry, trigonometry, calculus), and social skills.

2.4.3 Teaching Reading Strategies

Teaching reading strategies usually starts with modeling through a read-aloud. Choose a text to share and be sure to pre-read that book and prepare for places that you will stop to model the mental images that you are creating. You may want to have a whiteboard or chart paper available to actually draw, or have the drawings prepared ahead of time, to show your students when explaining your mental images. You can also draw your mental images on post-it notes and place them on the actual page in the story that sparked the mental image. Again, these images can be drawn in real time with students or prepared ahead of time to share with the students as you get to that part in the story. Be sure to showcase all 5 senses when describing your mental picture.

When teaching readers to visualize, it is crucial to choose a text that will support this strategy. Be sure to choose a book that is full of descriptive language and details. Students will need ample time to practice this strategy with you in guided reading or strategy groups as well as with their independent books. In all settings, students will need simple visuals to help them remember to use this strategy often. For example, a bookmark highlighting the strategy will help remind students to visualize while independent reading, or while reading in small groups.

Likewise, a colorful classroom poster to refer to is also a friendly reminder to keep creating mental images while reading. Create a bulletin board set where you begin to highlight each reading strategy as you introduce them to your students. Students can refer to the bulletin board all year long! Create on-going anchor charts of the mental images that you are creating during read-aloud modeling. These mental images, along with any written descriptions that you include with them will serve as great examples for students when creating their own mental images.

Visualizing is an important reading strategy that good readers use to help create mental images or movies in their minds to represent the ideas that they read in the text. Visualization requires students to weave together their own background knowledge, text evidence, and creativity to make an image in their mind's eye to match the story or informational article that they are reading. The images that they make help them to understand what they are reading at a deeper level. Visualizing is my favorite reading strategy to teach since it is not only fun for students but truly helps them to dig deeper into what they are reading. It is highly engaging for students and its interactive nature helps readers of all levels, including struggling readers, connect with the text. In fact, I have watched struggling readers blossom as readers when they put this reading strategy into action. As we teach students to make mental pictures and visualize as they read, we must provide students with opportunities to practice pulling their own background knowledge and gathering important language from the text to help create their own creative mental image of the books that they are reading to understand the text at a deeper level.

3. Objectives of Study

The specific objectives of the study were to:

1. Identify the effectiveness of the “Buncee Add Smart” method in language subjects among remedial pupils.
2. Identify the effectiveness scores of remedial pupils in the pre-test and post-test before and after using the “Buncee Add Smart” method.

4. Hypothesis

Ho: There is no significant difference between the test scores of group A remedial pupils and group B remedial pupils based on the “Buncee Add Smart” method and the traditional method.

H1: There is a significant difference between the test scores of group A remedial pupils and group B remedial pupils based on the “Buncee Add Smart” method and the traditional method.

Ho: There is no significant difference between pre-test and post-test of remedial pupils in Malay language subject.

H2: There is a significant difference between pre-test and post-test of remedial pupils in Malay language subject.

5. Research of Methodology

This study includes a quantitative study and it can be classified into quasi-experimental research. The research design uses a pre-test and post-test with none-equivalent groups which involve a group of students who belong to the experimental class and another class as the control class. According to Kothari [16], the principle of an experimental study is that if two identical groups are taken, one of which is given special treatment and the other is no. In this study, the special treatment given is the “Buncee Add Smart” in teaching language subjects.

The researchers organized pre-test in both classes for learning new vocabulary in language subjects before the two classes were given treatments. Afterwards, the researcher gave the “Buncee Add Smart” to class A as the experimental class and a traditional method was provided to class B as the control class. After organizing the pre-test for the two classes, the researchers administered the post-test to both to see the students’ achievement after the treatments were provided.

The main purpose of this study was to investigate and identify the effectiveness of using “Buncee Add Smart” in teaching language subjects on learning new vocabulary among remedial pupils. The Malay language subject was chosen to assess the effect on remedial pupils by using “Buncee Add Smart” because it is fundamental to all subjects in elementary schools.

Conducting a pilot test is to confirm the reliability, validity, and internal consistency of the test questions, followed by field testing methods, which was used to identify the effectiveness of

“Buncee Add Smart”. Data analysis involved a quantitative research approach using a paired t-test to find the difference in scores between the pre-test and post-test. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to analyse and find the relationships between improvements in scores and variables.

10 participants were randomly selected from all the remedial pupils. The ability of this group of remedial pupils was measured three times within a period of six months from July 2020 to January 2021 to collect data of their performance in one of the primary schools. They were coming from different classes and had a variety of learning disabilities. Class A consisted of 5 remedial pupils [4(80%) girls and 1(20%) boys] were diagnosed with reading and writing disabilities. Class B consisted of 5 remedial pupils [3(60%) girls and 2(40%) boys] were also diagnosed with reading and writing disabilities. Class A was provided with the “Buncee Add Smart” method. However, class B was taught by the traditional method. The pupils of class B were conducted by using the flashcards for learning the new vocabulary.

There is one set of instruments prepared for checking how much vocabulary has been acquired by the students. There are only pictures and words for choosing the correct answers. The score of the instrument is 20 marks by counting how many correct answers. The higher marks get means the more vocabulary has been learned within six months.

6. Data Analysis & Findings

This study aimed to reveal whether the use of the “Buncee Add smart” method is more effective than that of the traditional method to learn new vocabulary in relation to students’ performance. The T-test was used to assess whether there is any difference between students’ performance taught by using the “Buncee Add smart” method. The study was conducted during a period of six months from July 2020 to January 2021 for remedial pupils.

The data was collected through pre-test and post-test by using T-test In this research, the measurements are repeated three times in order to identify the difference in their performance. The tests were given to the remedial pupils before and after the treatments. The paired t- test was carried out to assess whether a significant difference exists between pre-test and post-test for repeated measurements. The data was collected from pre-test and post-test in the Malay language subject.

Table 1: The scores of effectiveness of the “Buncee Add Smart” method after three months

GROUP	PRE-TEST THE MALAY LANGUAGE SUBJECT	POST-TEST THE MALAY LANGUAGE SUBJECT
A	2	15
A	4	18
A	3	15
A	5	19
A	3	16

Table 2: The scores of the traditional method after three months

GROUP	PRE-TEST THE MALAY LANGUAGE SUBJECT	POST-TEST THE MALAY LANGUAGE SUBJECT
B	2	7
B	3	8
B	4	7
B	2	6
B	3	9

Table 3 : The mean value for Group A and Group B.

Group Statistics	CLASS	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
SCORES FOR 2 GROUPS	GROUP A	5	16.6	1.81659	0.8124
	GROUP B	5	7.4	1.14018	0.5099

Table 4 : The Independent-samples T-test between Group A and Group B.

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
SCORES FOR 2 GROUPS	Equal variances assumed			9.592	8	0	9.2	0.95917	6.98816	11.41184
	Equal variances not assumed	2.753	0.136	9.592	6.728	0	9.2	0.95917	6.91322	11.48678

The t-test results are significant ($t = 9.592$, $df = 8$, $P < 0.05$). There is a difference between remedial pupils in group A and group B who were taught by the “Bunce Add Smart” method and the traditional method. The mean difference value of 9.2 shows that in the population from which sample is drawn, the group A remedial pupils in teaching the “Bunce Add smart” method (mean score=16.6) were more effective than group B remedial pupils in teaching the traditional method (mean score= 7.4).

Table 5 : The Paired-samples statistics between pre-test and post-test.

Paired Samples Statistics		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	TRADITIONAL	3.4	5	1.14018	0.5099
	BUNCEE ADD SMART	16.6	5	1.81659	0.8124

Table 5 : The Paired-samples correlations between pre-test and post-test.

Paired Samples Correlations		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	TRADITIONAL & BUNCEE ADD SMART	5	0.941	0.017

Table 5 : The Paired-samples T-test between pre-test and post-test.

		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	TRADITIONAL - BUNCEE ADD SMART	-13.2	0.83666	0.37417	14.23885	12.16115	-35.278	4	0

The paired-samples T-test table showed that the research result is significant ($t = -35.278$, $df = 4$, $p < 0.05$). The null hypothesis is rejected and there is a difference in the result of remedial pupils' average score in the pre-test and post-test for Malay language subject. The mean score value is higher after applying the “Bunce Add smart” method which is 16.6 compared to the traditional method with only 3.4 (based on table 5). This showed the result of remedial pupils' average score being able to increase with the “Bunce Add smart” method.

7. Discussion

The first set of findings to address the Research Question 1 revealed that there is a significant difference between the test scores of group A remedial pupils and group B remedial pupils based on the “Buncee Add Smart” method and the traditional method. The “Buncee Add smart” method was more effective than that to enhance students’ learning for Malay language subject. It would be proved that visual learners tend to be holistic learners who process information best when it is presented to them as a robust whole rather than piecemeal, they tend to see positive educational outcomes when they are presented with summarizing charts and diagrams rather than sequential slides of information. [10]

The indicator of this was the mean score of students who were taught by using the “Buncee Add smart” method was higher than that of those who were treated by using the traditional method. By applying the traditional method, remedial pupils find it difficult to sit down and stay focused in class and most of them have to give more attention by using interactive digital tools such as “Buncee Add smart” method. In addition, the delivery of traditional methods does not grasp the attention of all learning types. In fact, studies estimate that somewhere between 50 and 70 percent of the population have affinities to several different styles of learning. [14] These people are called “multimodal learners” and tend to succeed in classroom settings that engage them with multiple learning styles alternately or in concert with one another. Educators also find it hard to differentiate the instruction of the class's learning through diverse students’ learning styles such as auditory, kinesthetic and visual.

The second set of findings to address Research question 2 indicated that there is a significant difference between pre-test and post-test of remedial pupils in Malay language subject. The “Buncee Add smart” method has prepared all the learning tools which were suitable for remedial pupils. 5 of remedial pupils were indicated with the higher, mean score after the post-test. Visualizing is an important reading strategy that good readers use to help create mental images or movies in their minds to represent the ideas that they read in the text. Visualization requires students to weave together their own background knowledge, text evidence, and creativity to make an image in their mind's eye to match the story or informational article that they are reading. The images that they make help them to understand what they are reading at a deeper level. Visualizing is my favorite reading strategy to teach since it is not only fun for students but truly helps them to dig deeper into what they are reading. It is highly engaging for students and its interactive nature helps readers of all levels, including struggling readers, connect with the text. “Buncee add smart” method is fun and interesting to improve students’ imagination and the graphics have attracted the visual learners. This method also can take advantage of remedial pupils to speak, practice or read aloud vocabulary with repetition. They were able to apply self-learning at home without teachers' guidance.

Every student has a handphone, an ipad or a computer in order to follow the generation of artificial intelligence. Connectivism allows students to incorporate electronic devices for the “off-site” storage of information, treating the role of memory differently than prior learning theories. Before technology appeared on the pedagogical landscape, the cognitivist method was delivery of instruction by a teacher-centered method. Students were receivers of the information. Traditional methods were no longer an effective method to improve students’ performance. In the constructivist model, learners became dynamic members in the development of their learning while the teacher served as facilitator. [3] In the post-technology world, Siemens proposed “connectivism as a learning theory for the digital age”. [4] Students have the potential to play an important role in interacting with the digital world.

Nevertheless, a noteworthy observation from the post-test assessment is that the poor performance by the children in the pre-test assessment significantly improved after the interventions and especially after practice and training by using the “Buncee Add Smart” method. Although the pupil's performance in the post-test improved immediately after applying the “Buncee Add Smart” method, the results reveal that the pupil's new vocabulary knowledge and word reading improved significantly. This means the remedial pupils improved their knowledge of letters and words even in the extremely short time. According to [17], children who performed poorly even after training and practice might have needed more time and repetition to learn letter-sound correspondences, which is the most essential skill in learning to read. Children's individual differences in reading performance depends on the child's memory for sounds and the rate at which he or she can retrieve the sounds from short-term memory.

8. Conclusion

The “Buncee Add smart” method can enhance students' learning new vocabulary skills because it contains a process of monitoring the results of the interpretation. This technique also can encourage students to learn, listen, and attain a good understanding of texts being read. The study showed that the “Buncee Add smart” method has a relatively high impact in improving remedial students' achievement, especially in reading and listening skills. As discussed at the beginning, digital tools have the potential to produce active learning. The “Buncee Add smart” method was a new innovation to release the boredom and tiredness of remedial students. In an effort to strengthen the teaching of basic reading and writing skills, teachers have to create more creative and interactive materials through the “Buncee Add smart” method. Therefore, strong effects of the remedial teachers could increase the excellence of remedial pupils in learning new vocabulary skills.

Furthermore, there was significant improvement in the mean scores (with regard to pre-test and post-test scores) among remedial pupils. Learning how to read is also complicated by limited access to reading materials, and large classes. The results point strongly to the need for the government to ease the burden on teachers by finding the best ways to make teaching and learning easy for both children and teachers, who are at times overwhelmed by having to teach so many children. From the study results, the “Buncee Add smart” method seems to be one of the best ways. The “Buncee Add smart” method can be used as a tool for supplementing the acute shortage of reading materials in primary schools. Students do not have interesting material to read for them to automatise their skills to become functional for reading acquisition. The “Buncee Add smart” method will provide teachers with additional assistance that will help children to learn new vocabulary as well. In the future, “Buncee Add smart” method will be able to be used in other subjects such as mathematics and sciences which need more interactive teaching tools to improve students' learning in advance.

References

- Corcoran, J., & Carlson, C. C. (1994). *The teacher who couldn't read*. Colorado Springs, CO: Focus on the Family.
- Fiore, A. (August 17 2017). How can a theory guide or inform practice? [Web log post]. Retrieved December 21, 2018, from <http://annemariefiore.com/connectivism/>
Retrieved on July 1, 2019, from [researchgate.net/publication/241605288](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/241605288) *Not Another Inventory Rather a Catalyst f or Reflection*
Retrieved on July 1, 2019, from vark-learn.com/introduction-to-vark/the-vark-modalities/
Retrieved on July 1, 2019, from child1st.com/blogs/resources/visual-learners-and-how-they-learn
Retrieved on July 1, 2019, from medium.com/@homespunandhandson/vark-learning-styles-the-auditory-learner-90ce0fd434ed
Retrieved on July 1, 2019, from teachhub.com/vark-model-teaching-strategies
Retrieved on July 1, 2019, from medium.com/@homespunandhandson/vark-learning-styles-the-kinesthetic-learner-5109618d03e4
Retrieved on July 1, 2019, from vark-learn.com/strategies/multimodal-strategies/
Retrieved on July 1, 2019, from edutopia.org/multimodal-learning-teaching-methods-media
- Kothari, C. R. (2004). *Research methodology: Methods and techniques*. New Age International.
- Lyytinen, H. (2009). Learning and learning disabilities in Africa.
- Mounia, A. B. I. K., Ajhoun, R., & Ensias, L. (2012). Impact of technological advancement on pedagogy. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 13(1), 224-237.
- Siemens, G. (2004). Connectivism: A learning theory for the digital age. elearnspace.
- Siemens, G. (June 16 2012). The future of higher education. Retrieved June 16, 2014. from <http://www.elearnspace.org/blog/2012/06/16/the-future-of-higher-education-and-other-imponderables/>
- Siemens, G. (June 3 2012). What is the theory that underpins our MOOCs? [Blog post]. Retrieved from <http://www.elearnspace.org/blog/2012/06/03/what-is-the-theory-that-underpins-our-moocs/>
- Stavredes, T. (2011). *Effective online teaching: Foundations and strategies for student success*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Torgesen, J.K. (1985). *Memory processes in reading disabled children*. *Journal of Learning Disabilities*, 18, 350-358. doi: 10 -1177/002221948501800607.